

Range expansion of the Five-lined Skink *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* into the southern Sinai, Egypt

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INTRODUCTION

The Five-lined Skink (*Mabuya quinquetaeniata*) is a species with a mainly central African distribution (SPAWLS et al., 2002). The most northerly populations occur in the Nile region in Egypt (SALEH, 1997). In the desert habitat of Egypt, the species is bound to relatively humid habitats bordering the Nile. The Gulf of Suez and the Suez Channel separate the Sinai Desert from the Egyptian mainland. BAHA EL DIN (1992) predicted a possible range expansion of this species into the northern Sinai from the mainland as a result of continuing water irrigation projects and related cultivation within this desert. That *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* has colonised the southern Sinai as well, is confirmed by my find of an isolated population near Sharm el Sheikh as documented below.

Distribution of *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* in Egypt (after: SALEH, 1997).

A male *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* in the hotel garden near Sharm el-Sheikh.

Photo: J. van der Winden

OBSERVATIONS

On January 15th 2001 I visited the Sharm el Sheikh area for the first time. In one of the hotel gardens I observed briefly a large rock dwelling skink, obviously a species of *Mabuya*. Unfortunately I could not find it after it fled and was therefore unable to determine the species. As *Mabuya* skinks do not occur in this part of the Sinai, I was sure that this was an unusual observation. In January 2004, I was able to visit the same area again and took the opportunity to return to the hotel garden on January 2nd and 3rd. On both days I found several skinks and this time I was able to take pictures. In total at least three adult males and 10 to 15 subadults or females were observed. All specimens were identified as Five-lined Skinks, *Mabuya quinquetaeniata*. I was able to exclude the somewhat similar Rainbow Skink (*Mabuya margaritifera*) from the identification based on the uniform brown dorsal scale coloration of the males and the five whitish to yellow dorsolateral stripes on females and subadults of *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* (cf. SPAWLS et al., 2002). All animals were observed in the extended gardens of the Royal Paradise Resort in the

A young female *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* in the hotel garden near Sharm el-Sheikh.

Foto: J. van der Winden

Phantasia area between Sharm el Sheikh and Nama'a Bay. This is a recently developed tourist area in the bare coastal desert. The desert is now well irrigated and the new gardens are richly vegetated with palm trees, flowering bushes, herbs and grasses. The skinks were widely distributed over the hotel garden near small stone heaps, stone walls, stairs, water reservoirs and fountains. When disturbed, they hid in walls, stone heaps or in well-grown bushes with grasses underneath. The animals were active from 10:00 until 16:00. In the vicinity of the resort, more comparable garden areas were present but these were not checked for lizards. No comparable areas of natural origin exist nearby.

DISCUSSION

As far as was known, *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* did not occur in the southern Sinai Peninsula, although it was expected for the northern part (WERNER, 1982; BAHHA EL DIN, 1992), where its occurrence was recently confirmed (Baha el Din, pers. comm.). In other former desert areas in Egypt, such as the Hurghada region, which has now been developed for the tourist industry, the species is also known from recent years (Baha El Din, pers. comm.). The northern part of the Sinai and the Hurghada area borders are still more or less related to the original distribution area of this species.

My finding of an isolated population in the extreme south of the Sinai suggests a deliberate or accidental introduction of this species. Not only is the desert currently irrigated by man and therefore provides suitable possible habitats, but many plants, like palms and other garden decorations, were transported from other parts of Egypt into the Sharm el Sheikh region. It is possible that specimens of this skink were transported with palm trees or other transplants into the garden area. The population seems to be flourishing in the area, at least for the last

Hotel gardens at Sharm el-Sheikh en Nama'a Bay.

three years, and the possibilities for expansion into other hotel gardens are vast. It therefore is likely that as long as these artificial habitats exist, a sustainable population of this species will be present in the area. Many wintering bird species with higher dispersion rates such as Bluethroat (*Luscinia svecica* ssp.), Chiffchaff (*Phylloscopus collybita* ssp.) and Pied Wagtail (*Motacilla alba*) preceded *Mabuya quinquetaeniata* into this region.

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SUMMARY

On the 2nd and 3rd of January 2004 a population of the Five-lined Skink (*Mabuya quinquetaeniata*) was discovered in Sharm el Sheikh, Sinai (Egypt) in a hotel garden. This species was formerly unknown from the southern Sinai. It was able to expand its range because of tourist developments in the dry desert with correlating irrigation projects. It is presumed that specimens of this lizard were accidentally transported into the region, e.g. in palm trees, from the Egyptian mainland.

LITERATURE

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